

INNOVATION PROCESSES IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN CHINA

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Аннотация: В статье освещены инновационные процессы образования в Китае. Мировое сообщество все больше смотрит на Китай как на страну с быстро растущим уровнем грамотности населения, высоким уровнем образования в ведущих вузах. С одной стороны, количество китайских студентов, выезжающих на учебу за границу, растет, с другой - правительство увеличивает квоты на количество иностранных преподавателей. Правительство Китая и его руководство постоянно работают над созданием механизма взаимной поддержки и взаимодействия правительства, общества, семьи и образовательного учреждения, формируют благоприятный общественный климат, способствующий здоровому росту школьников и студентов и постоянному совершенствованию образовательной системы. предоставление возможности учиться в любом возрасте. В планах Министерства образования Китая сформулированы новые ориентиры.

Ключевые слова: образование, инновации, университет, международное сообщество, образовательные достижения, колледж, учебные заведения, образовательная деятельность, педагогика Китая.

Annotation: The article highlighted the innovation processes of education in China, The international community looks at China as on the country with quickly growing level of literacy of the population, high education level in the leading higher education institutions more and more. On the one hand, the number of the Chinese students who are going abroad for study grows, with another – the government increases quotas of the number of foreign teachers. the government of China and its management constantly work on creation of the mechanism of mutual support and interaction of the government, society, a family and educational institution, form the favorable public climate promoting healthy growth of pupils and students and continuous improvement of the educational system providing an opportunity to study at any age. In plans of the Ministry of Education of China new reference points are formulated.

Key words: education, innovation, university, international community, education achievements, college, teaching institutions, educational activities, pedagogy of China.

In plans of the Ministry of Education of China new reference points are formulated: in 2020 about 13,5 thousand experts with the higher education and about 31 thousand with an average will fall on 100 thousand people, and illiteracy and semi-literacy will decrease to 3 percent and below. The average period of training will come to eleven years instead of nine years now.

According to the report of UNESCO "Education for all", China took the place, the second after India, in the world by the number of illiterate adult citizens – 224 million people. It is about a quarter of all illiterate people of the world. Nearly 80 percent of Chinese lived in rural areas where they sometimes couldn't get even senior secondary education, not to mention the highest. Countrywide only 60 graduates of higher educational institutions were the share of

each 10 thousand people. But this situation has changed by 2003 when the Asian giant began to win first place in the world on scales of the higher education¹.

Educational achievements of Chinese should be estimated, taking into consideration a situation in the countries, at least partly comparable to China on the passable historical way, and also on the number and structure of the population. As base for such comparisons there is a sense first of all to consider the Asian states. On their background especially obvious is serious progress of the People's Republic of China.

So, in difference, for example, from India China is the country with the fast-growing level of literacy of the population, including country, making bulk in both countries. Illiterate in China are only 15 percent of adult population! Whereas in India this percent equals 47, in Bangladesh – 61, in Pakistan – 59, in Iran – 27, in Turkey – 17, in Indonesia – 15. Even better at the People's Republic of China other important indicator – a share of illiterate women in age group from 15 to 24 years. He shows efficiency of fight against illiteracy for the last twenty-twenty five years and indirectly testifies to position of women in a family and society. In China the specified indicator makes only 4 percent (in India – 44, in Bangladesh – 63, in Pakistan – 61, in Iran – 10, in Turkey – 8, in Indonesia – 4).

The general structure of education in China consists of several steps and includes elementary and high school, and also the higher and secondary vocational education. An initial step – preschool education (kindergartens, children of three-five years). About 140 million people, training term – study six years at elementary school.

At high school there are more than 60 million pupils. The following step – compulsory nine years' education. Initial and incomplete average schools in parallel practice educational systems "six and three", "five and four" or "nine years in a row". After a devyatiletka pupils can be admitted to full high school (in Chinese – highest average) where it is necessary to study three more years, that is total period of study will make twelve years. It is possible to get secondary vocational (professional) education also: after 9 classes the term of training makes four years, after 12 classes – two. Higher education institutions practice system, habitual for us, too: on full-time departments training lasts five years (at medical institutes – seven-eight). The higher education can be two types: or according to the program of the expert, or two-level, on system the bachelor plus the master. After obtaining the diploma about the higher education study in postgraduate study for receiving degree of the doctor of philosophy is possible.

At the second stage, in the 90th years, obligatory have defined nine years' education. Now receives it to 98 percent of youth. "Changes in system of the higher education of the People's Republic of China impress. According to figures, in 1949 only 205 state universities, now – more than 2 thousand worked in the country, and the number of students makes more than 20 million people. Thanks to consecutive reforms initial scales of system of the higher education to People's Republic of China continue to be improved in recent years. In 1993 creation of system of 100 universities of the first-class world level therefore 708 higher education institutions of the country have been united in 302 versatile universal higher education institutions has begun. In particular, the Central academy of applied art has been combined with the most authoritative temple of science of China – Qinghua university"¹. The Beijing university existing more than hundred years was united with the medical school, best in the country, – the Beijing medical academy. Merge of such educational institutions has

allowed to carry out deep changes in a control system of the higher education, to optimize and to rationally place pedagogical resources, to increase quality of teaching and level of educational process. The special state fund of support over 30 higher education institutions which are among the advanced higher educational institutions of the world is created. High education level in the leading higher education institutions of the People's Republic of China recognizes also the international community. So, the research structure of the international higher education of QS in 2010 has published a new rating of the leading higher education institutions of the world where the Syangansky university, Syangansky university of science and technologies, Syangan university of Chinese and the Beijing university have got to the first fifty. The Qinghua university was placed on the 54th line, Taiwan – on the 94th. The Syangan university has for the first time outstripped Tokyo and has won first place among higher educational institutions of Asia.

To increase quality of training in higher educational institutions, the government of the People's Republic of China intends to increase considerably quotas of the number of foreign teachers in China. The priority in this context will be given, first of all, to teachers from Russia, Ukraine and countries of Eastern Europe. Most of foreign teachers will be distributed in higher education institutions of the southern and southeast provinces of China as universities of these areas are in more favorable financing terms.

For attraction of the latest technologies from abroad in the country there is a practice of creation of so-called zones of technical and economic development where scientific researches and direct use of results of scientific developments in practice are at the same time conducted. Here the optimum investment climate is created, taxation tariffs are lowered, joint basic scientific researches with foreign experts are conducted. ZTER play a large role in respect of stimulation of an exchange with foreign countries, including through education.

Besides, in China higher education and the higher education on the basis of an ex-sloe quickly develops. In the country the system of postgraduate education is created. With introduction of compulsory education in the People's Republic of China also allocations for needs of education have considerably increased, training conditions have qualitatively improved, skills of pedagogical personnel were improved. Today there is practically no school in the province where educational classes wouldn't be equipped state-of-the-art. The government cares for maintenance of the status of pedagogical work, salary increase. The general management of the sphere of the higher education of China is still performed by the State Council through the Ministries of Education and departments subordinated to him. The state encourages creation and financing of higher education institutions by professional, enterprise, public collectives and organizations, certain citizens within the law. Thereby for the first time in principle the idea of establishment and legalization of the private higher school is allowed. At the same time it is emphasized that service to interests of the state and society, but not generation of profit has to be the purpose of creation of higher education institution in the People's Republic of China.

“The structure of specialties is gradually rationalized. Now the higher school of the People's Republic of China trains masters in 820 directions. Technical specialties and fundamental sciences are in percentage terms priority. The second place is taken by pedagogical professions that is explained by their demand labor market”.¹

In the modernized China higher education institutions have been given big freedom in attraction of additional resources for development of science and technologies. Such types of commercial activity as rental of premises, publishing and typographical services and so on, extend more and more widely. The People's Republic of China made use of the western experience on foundation of industrial parks of high technologies. The authorities have defined four major scientific directions in which they are created: information technologies and technologies of new materials, electronic engineer, biotechnology, nanotechnology. Today in the country about 20 such parks located in suburbs of the densely populated industrial cities and concentrating research, design institutes, pilot productions, laboratories, proving grounds.

In the People's Republic of China there was actually a transition to self-financing, training in higher education institution became paid. At receipt in higher educational institutions examinations aren't taken. Qualification tests in the form of testing carry out once upon termination of school. For transfer it is necessary to gain 500 points. And it is necessary to pay 1 thousand yuans a year (about 4,5 thousand rubles) for each not gathered additionally point. On average the tuition fee fluctuates from 500 to 2 thousand dollars a year. And at the same time entrants still pass a rigid competition so about elimination the speech practically doesn't go.

At the expense of the state or with preferential payment only young people from the needing families or from distant rural areas can study. For progress in study they even have the right to apply for a grant and single social payments. As a result of reform students became more free in choice of profession, and universities have gained big independence in establishment and regulation of the list of specialties depending on requirements of society.

In the People's Republic of China the status of teachers is high. In 1985 at birthday of the philosopher Confucius the Teachers' Day which has become the country's first holiday of people of a separate profession has been founded. Since 1993 the law on teachers which has established the rights and duties of teachers, requirements at employment, social guarantees is entered. During reforms the salary of teachers has increased on average by 15 times and has exceeded 31 thousand yuans (4840 dollars) a year at teachers of the higher school and 15 thousand yuans (2340 dollars) at teachers of elementary and high schools. And by 2015 the salary of teachers and teachers has to increase still twice. As a result of the People's Republic of China became the owner of the biggest in the world of the teaching case (more than 12,5 million people). And this figure constantly increases.

The government of the People's Republic of China has developed the program for creation of the union of network training of teachers for increase of professional level of teachers. Her purpose – by means of informatization of education to promote modernizations of training of teachers, by means of an educational network for teaching personnel, satellite television and the Internet to provide the help and services in continuous retraining of teachers; to carry out large-scale, high-quality and comprehensive highly effective preparation and training of teachers of elementary and high schools for substantial increase of their professional level. Now among teachers of higher education institutions there are 9,5 percent of professors and 30 percent of associate professors. Youth and people of middle age are the leading force of pedagogics, in higher education institutions teachers at the age of 45 years and more young than 35 years make respectively 79 and 46 percent. Teachers of higher education institutions

widely conduct scientific researches, being the main hope in this area, as well as in intellectual and scientific and technical innovation. Today in all higher education institutions 280 academicians Academy of Sciences of China – 40,7 percent from total number of AN of China, 234 academicians of engineering sciences – 35,3 percent from total number of AIN of China work. Thus, the government of China and its management constantly work on creation of the mechanism of mutual support and interaction of the government, society, a family and educational institution, form the favorable public climate promoting healthy growth of pupils and students and continuous improvement of the educational system providing an opportunity to study at any age.

Used literature

- 1.Liu Gao Jie.The problem of the modernized China higher education institutions,- Beijing Normal University, 2014.-P.6-7.
- 2.Min Xo Yu. The problem of the doctrine is interdisciplinary // Journal of Educational Sotsiology.- China, 2009.-P.-29-30.